

Research and Human Values

Dr. Alka Singh
Assistant Professor (Music)
Dayanand Girls P.G. College,
Kanpur.

Change is the law of nature. we can see daily a new change around us. Most of those changes are beneficial for our society but not all the changes are beneficial. Research is the father of changes. Without research we can't bring any positive change in our society. Actually, Research is the combination of two words- Re + search. It means search again and again until can't find proper, true result. Research is the key for the betterment of human beings. So, it is our duty to participate in researches. Without true participation any researcher can't find proper result. At the grassroot level of research it is important that researcher should be very much concerned about the participant's privacy, their mentally, physically and emotionally security. All these ethical issues of research may be known as human values in research.

Human values in research: Historical Background

The issue of human values in research originated from the field of biomedical research. On 9th December, 1946, an American military tribunal opened criminal proceedings against 23 leading German physicians. They all conducted medical experiment on concentration camp prisoners without their consent. After the experiment most of the prisoners died or were permanently crippled. In 1948 **Nuremberg code** was established as the result of the trial. Nuremberg code is the first chapter in the history of human values in research. According to this code voluntary consent of human subjects or participants is mandatory.

Need of laws to maintain human values in research

Prior to 1974, there were many infamous researches in which researchers placed their participants at definite risk in their studies. In 1963, Stanley Milgram gave electric shocks of up to 450 volts to his participants. Laud Humphrey (1970) study of homosexuality was another controversial study because of its deception and gross invasion of privacy. Such types of studies were also conducted in India. So, all these studies prompted government to develop a unified set of laws for research.

Organizations and Reports about Human values in research

- AERA (American Educational Research Association), 1991
- APA (American Psychological Association)
- ASA (American sociological Association)
- WHO (World Health organization)
- National Research Act, 1974.
- Belmont Report, 1979.

All these are renowned organizations to maintain human values in research. All the researchers of India and other countries have to follow rules and laws which were described by these organizations. CDSCO (Central Drugs Standard Control Organization) is the Indian organization. This organization maintains human values in biomedical researches. Before the starting of any research IRB (Institutional Review Board) check the Research proposal. If all the ethical guidelines are followed in proposal, subjects are safe in study and human values are maintained in the research proposal then after the satisfaction of IRB members, researcher is permitted for study. It is such a long-process. For the permission, researcher fill a form. In this form he/she describes about the purposes of study, procedure, subjects, tools etc. Researcher has to submit consent letter of the subjects for permission also.

Human values in Research

Informed Consent

Informed consent is very important in every type of research. The researcher should tell all about the study to the participants e.g. research process, purpose, risks, benefits etc. After the satisfaction and permission of participants, researcher should start the study.

Avoid unethical questions and Biases

Researcher should not ask any unethical question to the participants. They should avoid questions regarding their income, their parents' studies, their caste, their religion, marital status etc. A researcher should be free from biases. She/he should be objective. Researcher should never get involved emotionally in the study. Results should be defined clearly as they are.

Confidentiality

The researcher should maintain strict confidentiality about the information obtained from the participants. Any personal information about participant should never be revealed by the researcher. Even in research record and research report researchers have to be very cared

about the personal information of the participants. Researcher should use words like-subjects, Participants, Chairperson, Baby etc. All these words hide, religion, gender, caste etc. of the participants.

Inform about the result

It is the basic right of the participants to know about the result of the study. So researcher should tell all about the result of the study to the participants. It is also duty of the researcher that he/she should not tell others about the role of every subject.

Respect for subjects

The researcher should be thankful to the participants. Researcher should protect physical, psychological, emotional integrity of the subjects. Every subject has right to withdraw any time from the study. Participants can ask any question, any time during the study.

All above are some main human values which should be followed in every research. All these values guide researcher and help them to conduct a fruitful research. In India, there are 1083 EC (Ethical committees) till 01 August, 2016. All these committees look after the human values in researches. Every research plays a very important role in the development of society but if researcher doesn't follow human values in the study, such study is not beneficial for the society. Human values are like soul for every research without soul body is dead and without following human values in research study is useless, not helpful for any new advancement in society.

References

1. Ary, Donald; Jacobs, Lucy Cheser and Sorensen, Chris (2010), Introduction to Research in Education (8th edition), Canada, Cengage Learning, 590-602
2. Giddens, Anthony (2011), Introduction to sociology, London, Seagull Publication, 12
3. Kour, Sunmeet (2014), Ethical and Legal issues in Educational Research, Indian Journal of Applied Research, 4(6), 133-135
4. Sambasivarao, T. (2017), Human Values in The Society, Global Journal For Research Analysis, 6(9), 102-103

5. Shanthini, B. (2018), An Empirical Study on Human Values- A Study with Reference to Adolescents, International Journal of Engineering Development And Research, 6(4), 422-426
6. Singh, Arun Kumar (2017), Manovigya, Samajshastra tatha Shiksha mei Shodh Vidhiyan, (13th edition) Delhi, Motilal Banarsidas, 01-29
7. Tripathy, Preety (2011), An Introduction to Moral Philosophy, New Delhi, Axis Publication, 01
8. Yip, Camille; Han, Nian-Lin Reena and Sng, Ban Leong (2016), Legal and Ethical Issues in Research, Indian Journal of Anesthesia, 60(9), 684-688, doi: 10.4103/0019-5049.190627